

TABLE 2—INFRARED DATA OF THE ADDUCTS OF HYDROXYPHENYLTELLURIUM TRICHLORIDE

Ligand	Interacting group	Stretching frequency (cm ⁻¹)	
		Pure ligand	Adduct
α -pic	-C=N	1574 s	1630 s
β -pic	-C=N	1576 s	1638 s
γ -pic	-C=N	1578 s	1640 s
bipy	-C=N	1560 s	1580 sh
Py	-C=N	1583 s	1640 m
phen	-C=N	1578 s	1595 m
Tea*	-C=N	1170 s	1145 sbr
Bds	-C=N	1630 m	1620 m
Ids	-C=N	1595 s	1580 s
TPPO	-P=O	1195 vs	1120 vs
TPAsO	-As=O	880 s	825 s
γ -picO	-N=O	1250 vs	1210 vs
DMSO	-S=O	1045 vs	980 vs
DMF	-C=O	1666 vs	1640 vs

* $\nu_{\text{sym}}(-\text{C}-\text{N})$ in Tea :at 830 cm⁻¹ undergoes negative shift and appears at 809 cm⁻¹.

$\nu_{\text{As}-\text{O}}$ in TPAsO undergo a negative shift in the complexes which suggests that these ligands are bonded to tellurium through the oxygen atom. This is also supported by a slight positive shift of $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$ in DMSO and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{N}}$ (contiguous to alkyl) in DMF¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

TGA measurements on a few representative adducts $p-\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{TeCl}_3 \cdot \text{L}$ (L=Py, bipy, γ -picO, DMSO) indicate slow continuous decomposition in the temperature range 120-600°, yielding a residue of Te metal. Unstable intermediates could not be identified.

The coordination number of the adducts in case of monodentate bases is limited to five while for bidentate ligands it is six.

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cis-Diacido Complexes of Pd(II) and Pt(II) with Pyrrolidine

MITHILESH ROY, A. K. UPADHYAY and L. K. MISHRA*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005 and

R. S. P. VERMA

Magadh University, Bodh Gaya

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COMPLEXES of Pd(II) and Pt(II) have been studied extensively¹⁻⁴ and are still of current interest due to their physiological properties and anti-cancer activity⁵. In the present note we are reporting the *cis*-diacido complexes of Pd(II) and Pt(II) with pyrrolidine (pyr).

Experimental

The ligand was obtained from Suchhardt (Germany) and palladium(II) chloride and chloroplatinic acid were obtained from Johnson-Mathey (London). Platinum(II) chloride was prepared by reducing H₂PtCl₆ by hydrazine hydrochloride⁶.

Preparation of the complexes :

[M(pyr)₂Cl₂] (M=Pd or Pt) : An aqueous acidic solution of metal chloride (pH 2-4) was treated with an excess of ligand with stirring till pH rose to 4-5. Palladium(II) complexes separated immediately while platinum(II) complexes separated on concentration and cooling to room temp. The products were collected, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over CaCl₂.

[M(pyr)₂X₂] (M=Pd or Pt; X=Br, I, NO₂ or NCS) : An aqueous suspension of [M(pyr)₂Cl₂] (0.5 g in ~30 ml) was refluxed with an excess of sodium or potassium salt of the appropriate anion on a steam bath for 1 to 2 hr. Pd(II) complexes separated on cooling, while Pt(II) complexes were obtained on concentrating and cooling the refluxate to room temp. The products were collected and dried as above.

The results of elemental analysis are given in Table 1. The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes was determined by Gouy method. The IR spectra of the complexes were recorded as KBr disc in the 4000-625 cm⁻¹ range at C.D.R.I., Lucknow and electronic reflectance spectra in

NOTES

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS, COLOUR AND ELECTRONIC REFLECTANCE BAND POSITIONS OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Electronic band positions (nm)
		Metal	Nitrogen	Halogen	
[Pd(pyr) ₂ Cl ₂]	Cream	33.68 (33.32)	8.42 (8.76)	22.86 (22.20)	400 sh
[Pd(pyr) ₂ Br ₂]	Cream	26.56 (26.06)	6.63 (6.85)	39.68 (39.14)	425 sh
[Pd(pyr) ₂ I ₂]	Orange yellow	21.71 (21.18)	5.86 (5.57)	50.01 (50.53)	440 sh
[Pd(pyr) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	Cream	31.58 (31.25)	16.10 (16.45)		380 sh
[Pd(pyr) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Cream	29.32 (29.19)	15.03 (15.36)		405 sh
[Pt(pyr) ₂ Cl ₂]	Cream	48.01 (47.81)	6.98 (6.86)	17.08 (17.37)	365 sh
[Pt(pyr) ₂ Br ₂]	Cream yellow	39.48 (39.26)	5.41 (5.63)	31.93 (32.16)	390 sh
[Pt(pyr) ₂ I ₂]	Cream yellow	32.83 (33.01)	4.69 (4.73)	43.18 (42.95)	410 m
[Pt(pyr) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	Cream	45.28 (45.46)	12.90 (13.05)		—
[Pt(pyr) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Cream yellow	43.48 (43.05)	12.06 (12.35)		360 sh

sh = shoulder ; m = medium.

TABLE 2

Infrared Spectral Band Positions in cm⁻¹

Compounds	$\nu(N-H)$	$\delta(N-H)$	Position of anion bands		
pyr	3260 s	1456 s			
[Pt(pyr) ₂ Cl ₂]	3215 vs	1462 s			
[Pt(pyr) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	3210 vs	1465 s	2150 m	2122 vs	705 m
[Pt(pyr) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	3200 vs	1468 s	1420 vs	1390 s	1350 vs
			890 s	820 m	
[Pd(pyr) ₂ Cl ₂]	3205 vs	1461 s			
[Pd(pyr) ₂ Br ₂]	3208 s	1463 s			
[Pd(pyr) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	3190 m	1468 m	2160 m	2110 vs	680 w
[Pd(pyr) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	3210 m	1465 m	1420 vs	1380 vs	1330 vs
			1275 m	826 s	812 m

s = strong, vs = very strong, m = medium.

visible region on Hilger-Watts UV spectrophotometer No. H-700.

Results and Discussion

Palladium(II) complexes have poor solubility but platinum(II) complexes dissolve appreciably in ethanol, methanol and aqueous medium. Both Pd(II) and Pt(II) complexes are diamagnetic, indicating 4-coordinated square planar structure with dsp² covalent bonding. The diffused reflectance spectra of Pd(II) complexes display a shoulder in the 380-440 nm region and of Pt(II) complexes in the 360-410 nm region, assignable to ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} transition in square planar field^{4,7}.

IR spectra :

Infrared spectra of pyr display (N-H) stretch at 3260 cm⁻¹ as a strong and sharp band which shifts to lower frequency by 45-70 cm⁻¹ in its complexes suggesting the coordination of the ligand through nitrogen atom^{8,9}. The strong to medium bands at 3000, 2990, 2880 and 2810 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectrum of the ligand are attributed to (C-H) stretches and their positions are not affected

appreciably but they are observed with reduced intensity. The (N-H) deformation band of pyr is observed at 1456 cm⁻¹ which is raised to higher frequencies by 6-12 cm⁻¹ in its complexes supporting the coordination of pyr through N-H nitrogen. The CH₂ deformation vibration of the ligand molecule is observed at 1440 and 1420 cm⁻¹ as strong bands and their positions remain unaffected in the complexes. The ir bands observed at 1335 (m), 1290 (w), 1112 (vs), 1060 (vs), 940 (s), 900 (s) and 882 (m) cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of pyrrolidine are attributed to $\nu(C-C)$, $\nu(C-N)$, -CH₂-wagging, scissoring, rocking and (NH) out-of-plane bending modes of vibrations¹¹. The positions of these bands are not affected appreciably in the complexes. The ir spectra of thiocyanate complex [Pd(pyr)₂(SCN)₂] display $\nu(C\equiv N)$ band at 2160 (m) and 2112 (s) and $\nu(C=S)$ at 680 cm⁻¹, while [Pt(pyr)₂(SCN)₂] exhibits $\nu(C\equiv N)$ at 2150 (m) and 2122 (s) and $\nu(C=S)$ band 705 cm⁻¹ (weak), similar to sulphur bonded thiocyanate group in *cis*-position^{10,12}. The ir spectrum of [Pd(pyr)₂(NO₂)₂] displays $\nu_{as}(NO_2)$ at 1420 and 1382, $\nu_s(NO_2)$ at 1330 and 1275 and $\delta(NO_2)$ at 826 and 812 cm⁻¹ while NO₂ vibrations of [Pt(pyr)₂(NO₂)₂] are observed at 1422 and 1390 (ν_{as}), 1350 and 1318 $\nu_s(NO_2)$ and 830 and 820 cm⁻¹ due to $\delta(NO_2)$, similar to *cis*-bonded nitro group around square planar Pt(II) complexes¹³. The ir spectra of the dihalo complexes could not be recorded in far infrared region and therefore nothing could be said about (M-N) and (M-X) vibrations. However, *cis* structure is also suggested for dihalo complexes in analogy with the dinitro complexes.

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**(Chloro) bis(π -methylcyclopentadienyl)-
N-Aryldithiocarbamato Zirconium(IV)
Complexes**

N. K. KAUSHIK*, M. S. YADAV, G. S. SODHI
and
B. BHUSHAN

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi,
Delhi-110 007

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accepted 28 April 1983*

In earlier communications¹⁻⁴, we reported a number of organometallic compounds involving dithiocarbamate ligands. Our interest in the investigation of bonding mode of the dithiocarbamate groups, prompted us to synthesise and characterise a number of (chloro) bis(π -methylcyclopentadienyl)-N-aryldithiocarbamato zirconium(IV) complexes. IR spectral studies indicate that the dithiocarbamate group is bidentate in these complexes.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets using Perkin Elmer grating spectrophotometer, Model 621. Electronic spectra were run on a Perkin Elmer 4000A instrument. Conductance measurements were made on a Beckmann conductivity bridge, Model RC-18A. Magnetic measurements were made by Gouy's method, using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as the calibrant.

Ammonium salts of dithiocarbamic acids were prepared by the method of Klopping and Kerk⁵. (π -CH₃C₅H₄)₂ZrCl₂ was prepared by the reaction of zirconium tetrachloride and bis(methylcyclopentadiene) in THF⁶. Nitrobenzene was purified for

conductance measurements by the method described by Fay *et al*⁷. Zirconium, nitrogen and sulphur were estimated by standard methods⁸.

All the complexes were prepared by a similar method. A solution of (π -CH₃C₅H₄)₂ZrCl₂ was refluxed with calculated amounts of ammonium dithiocarbamates for 12-14 hr. The contents were filtered while hot and the filtrate concentrated under vacuum at room temp. Petroleum ether (60-80°) was added to the concentrated filtrate and the mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The products were obtained as white or pale yellow crystals. These were filtered, washed with petroleum ether and recrystallised from an acetone solution by the addition of petroleum ether.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of (π -CH₃C₅H₄)₂ZrCl₂ with ammonium salts of dithiocarbamic acids may be represented by the following general equation

The complexes are white or pale yellow in colour. They are thermally quite stable. The compounds are soluble in THF, DMSO and acetone and partially soluble in halogenated hydrocarbons. Conductance measurements show that all the complexes are essentially non-electrolytes in nitrobenzene. Magnetic susceptibility measurements at room temp. indicate that the complexes are diamagnetic. The electronic spectra exhibit a single broad band in the 27750-24250 cm⁻¹ region. This is assigned to the charge transfer band⁹, similar to that exhibited by the complexes having the metal ions in (n-1)d⁰ns⁰ electronic configuration. The analytical data and physical characteristics of the complexes are listed in Table 1.

Whether the dithiocarbamate group is monodentate or bidentate is reflected in the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ stretching frequency. The 980-1050 cm⁻¹ region is associated with the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ stretching frequency. The presence of only one strong band in this region supports the bidentate behaviour of the dithiocarbamates, whereas the appearance of a doublet in this region indicates one complexed (C-S) group and one uncomplexed (C=S) group, that is monodentate bonding^{10,11}. The present complexes exhibit only a single absorption band at ~1000 cm⁻¹ which supports the bidentate and chelating nature of the dithiocarbamate ligand in all the cases.

The thioureide group, S=C-N, in case of dithiocarbamate complexes absorbs at ~1500 cm⁻¹^{12,13}. The frequency of this band lies intermediate to the C-N bond (1200-1300 cm⁻¹) and the C=N (1650-1700 cm⁻¹) stretching vibrations. In the present complexes, the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching frequency absorbs in the range 1380-1420 cm⁻¹. The occurrence of this band at a lower energy as